

EFFECTIVENESS OF SOCIAL REHABILITATION OF PATIENTS WITH ISCHEMIC STROKE AT THE OUTPATIENT STAGE

Turdiyev Ulugbek Narzullayevich

Bukhara State Medical Institute named after Abu Ali Ibn Sina

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ABSTRACT

Post-stroke rehabilitation plays a crucial role in restoring patients' functional independence, cognitive abilities, and reintegration into social life. Despite rapid advances in outpatient and remote rehabilitation methods, a number of barriers—such as speech disorders, loss of balance, domestic conditions, and social factors—continue to hinder effective recovery. At the same time, transcranial magnetic stimulation (TMS) is considered a promising and highly effective method in post-stroke rehabilitation. The relevance of this study is determined by the need to assess the effectiveness of TMS at the outpatient stage in comparison with standard rehabilitation..

Relevance of the Study: Post-stroke rehabilitation plays a crucial role in restoring patients' functional independence, cognitive abilities, and reintegration into social life. Despite rapid advances in outpatient and remote rehabilitation methods, a number of barriers—such as speech disorders, loss of balance, domestic conditions, and social factors—continue to hinder effective recovery. At the same time, transcranial magnetic stimulation (TMS) is considered a promising and highly effective method in post-stroke rehabilitation. The relevance of this study is determined by the need to assess the effectiveness of TMS at the outpatient stage in comparison with standard rehabilitation.

Purpose of the Study: To evaluate the impact of TMS used during outpatient rehabilitation on functional independence, neurological status, and cognitive functions in post-stroke patients compared with standard rehabilitation.

Materials and Methods

Patients with ischemic stroke were included in the study and divided into three groups according to stroke duration (1–3 months, 3–6 months, 6–12 months).

Two major groups were formed: Main group (MG): TMS + Choline alfoscerate + standard rehabilitation, Control group (CG): Standard rehabilitation only

Assessment criteria: Barthel Index (activities of daily living), Modified Rankin Scale (neurological deficit), NIHSS, ACE-R (cognitive function assessment), A remote rehabilitation platform and telemonitoring components were also used at the outpatient stage. Statistical significance was accepted at $p < 0.05$.

Results: Among the main reasons preventing patients from attending outpatient rehabilitation were: Speech disorders 14.8%, Loss of balance and frequent falls 18–24%, Domestic/social conditions 26–28%. In the TMS group, the Barthel Index increased from

69.9±0.86 to 89.3±0.7 ($p<0.0001$). In the standard rehabilitation group, it increased from 77.34±1.17 to 81.09±1.32 ($p<0.05$). Patients who achieved 91–100 points: TMS group 7%

Standard group 2%. Modified Rankin Scale, NIHSS, and ACE-R scores improved significantly across all duration-based groups in favor of TMS ($p<0.05$). Cognitive functions, speech parameters, balance, and independence in daily activities improved more rapidly and effectively in the TMS group. TMS also proved effective in remote/online rehabilitation by providing continuous communication with patients and ensuring individualized therapy.

Conclusion: The use of TMS during outpatient rehabilitation demonstrates significantly higher effectiveness compared with standard rehabilitation. TMS substantially improves functional independence, neurological and cognitive indicators, motor activity, and adaptation to daily life in post-stroke patients. The method ensures faster recovery, stable outcomes, and long-term positive effects within the rehabilitation process.

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